

Validating Doppler Reactivity Feedback Calculations Using SEFOR Isothermal and Power Ascending Experimental Data

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ABSTRACT

The Southwest Experimental Fast Oxide Reactor (SEFOR) was an experimental sodium-cooled fast breeder reactor operated from 1969 to 1972 with experiments designed to measure Doppler reactivity feedback in a large temperature range from around 350 °F (450 K) to temperatures approaching the melting point of mixed oxide fuel of around 5000 °F (3000 K), providing valuable data for code validations. Supported by the US Department of Energy (DOE) Fast Reactor Program (FRP), the experimental data obtained in the SEFOR tests were recently used to assess the reactivity feedback calculated by numerical tools that are widely used in US industry on designing sodium-cooled fast reactors (SFRs), i.e., deterministic codes such as the Argonne Reactor Computation (ARC) suite for reactor physics and the SAS4A/SASSYS-1 (SAS) code for fast reactor system analysis. All these codes are also at various levels of commercial-grade dedication by US SFR vendors to support their licensing efforts. The comparison of the calculated reactivity feedback with the measurement demonstrated accuracy of the derived fuel Doppler reactivity feedback from these simulations. The SEFOR experimental program includes isothermal tests, power ascending tests as well as reactivity insertion transient tests. This paper presents the work on modeling the isothermal tests and power ascending tests. Future work will continue to use these codes to simulate the reactivity insertion transients for assessing the numerical codes capabilities on modeling Doppler reactivity feedback in SFR transients.

Keywords: Reactivity feedback from fuel Doppler, SEFOR, isothermal tests, power ascending tests

1. INTRODUCTION

With several decades of advancements in computational tools for modeling nuclear reactor systems, numerical simulations have been critical steps and are widely performed in designing and licensing new advanced nuclear reactor systems, evaluating reactor safety and optimizing its performances. The United States Department of Energy's Office of Nuclear Energy (DOE-NE) Fast Reactor Program (FRP), under the Advanced Reactor Technologies (ART) portfolio, supports development of key technical elements needed by industry for enabling future large-scale commercialization of fast reactors in the United States. An important area supported by this program is leveraging data from past legacy experimental facilities to validate computational tools and methods that are used by industry for the design and licensing of advanced Sodium Fast Reactors (SFRs).

The Southwest Experimental Fast Oxide Reactor (SEFOR) was a sodium-cooled fast spectrum experimental facility which was built in Arkansas US and operated from 1969 to 1972. During this period, a three-phase experimental program was carried out to measure the Doppler reactivity feedback under various reactor conditions: Phase I - reactor startup and zero-power tests such as isothermal tests, Phase II - steady state power ascending tests, and Phase III - reactivity insertion transient tests [1-2]. This experimental program produced unique sets of measurement data on Doppler reactivity feedback in SFRs with a wide range of fuel temperatures from around 350 °F to temperatures approaching the melting point of the mixed oxide fuel of around ~5000 °F, providing valuable data for validating numerical tools.

This paper describes the US efforts on using the SEFOR experimental data to validate the reactor physics codes in the Argonne Reactor Computation (ARC) code suite [3] and the fast reactor system analysis code SAS4A/SASSYS-1 (SAS) [4] for modeling oxide fueled SFRs. Both codes are also at various levels of commercial-grade dedication by US SFR vendors to support their licensing efforts.

In particular, the ARC codes were used to compute the Doppler reactivity feedback in the SEFOR isothermal tests, and the ARC reactor physics codes as well as the SAS code were used to calculate the Doppler reactivity feedback in the power ascending tests. SEFOR core configurations and the isothermal tests and power ascending tests are described in Section 2. Section 3 describes the numerical simulations for the isothermal tests and its comparison to the experimental work, and Section 4 focuses on discussing the validation work on the power ascending tests.

2. SEFOR CORE CONFIGURATION AND EXPERIMENTS

SEFOR was a pool-type system with maximum operation power up to 20 MW. Its primary coolant entered the vessel through a single top inlet nozzle, flowed radially across the top, then down through the downcomer, turned upward passing the orifice zone and cooled the reactor core. The reactor core maximumly hosted about 109 hexagonal channels, each of them containing six $\text{UO}_2\text{-PuO}_2$ (MOX) fuel rod positions. The fuel rods were arranged around a central structure rod and were reinforced with six steel side rods. Critical core loadings were formed by loading fuel assemblies in an approximately cylindrical pattern as shown in Figure 1 a), in which core configuration I-E was the core configuration for the zero-power isothermal experimental tests and Core I-J for power ascending tests.

An engineering drawing of a standard SEFOR fuel assembly is shown in Figure 1 (b). The average fissile fuel in a regular fuel rod is about ~18.7% Pu-239 and Pu-241. Despite the regular fuel assemblies, the SEFOR core also used several variants in constructing different critical core configurations, such as those illustrated in Figure 1 a) for Core I-E and I-J. These variants included substitutions for standard fuel rods with a Guinea Pig (GP) rod with higher fissile concentration of ~ 25.0%, or with a B_4C rod, or with an instrumented fuel rod which has regular fuel compositions but has thermocouples embedded for measuring fuel center line temperatures at its middle plane or upper fuel region. A “DryWell” channel was at the center of the core and was mostly empty for housing the Fast Reactivity Excursion Device (FRED) during the Phase-III reactivity insertion transients.

Figure 1 c) illustrates the unique segmented design of the SEFOR fuel rods. Each rod incorporated nickel reflectors at both ends, depleted UO_2 insulation layers separating the $\text{PuO}_2\text{-UO}_2$ fuel into segments, and a top spring to hold all the different components securely in place. To mitigate reactivity feedback from fuel axial expansion, all standard fuel rods including GP rods also included a central spring to create an expansion gap. Two springs were used if the fuel rod was instrumented.

As illustrated in Figure 1 a), ten movable nickel reflectors were positioned outside the SEFOR reactor vessel. For shutdown, all reflectors were pushed down below the active fuel region providing about 10% of shutdown worth. For normal operation, core criticality was controlled by fine-tuning two reflector positions to maintain criticality, with other reflectors' positioned either fully up to cover the fuel region or fully down below the active core.

Isothermal tests were conducted in core configurations I-E with primary coolant gradually heated from 350 °F to 760 °F using a primary loop trace heating system. After reaching 760 °F, sodium was cooled to about 700 °F and was then reheated back to 760 °F. The heating rate was slow and was about 20 °F per hour. The radial reflector positions were adjusted to compensate for the negative reactivity feedback developed during the test. Reactor power was kept small and about 600 W. Coolant temperatures and reflector positions were recorded every 15 minutes. The negative reactivity was derived from the worth of the reflectors. The results include effects of Doppler broadening in nuclear reactions, thermal expansions of core as well as the expansion of sodium coolant in the reactor.

Power ascending steady state tests were conducted in Core I-J with reactor power raised stepwise from 0.4 MW to 17.5 MW. Negative reactivity feedback at higher power levels was offset also by adjusting the radial reflector positions. During the tests, the average coolant temperature over the active core was maintained at approximately 760 °F (677 K), while the inlet coolant temperature varied. Fuel temperature increases above the sodium coolant temperature were measured using thermocouples installed in the two Instrumented Fuel Assemblies (IFAs) with thermocouple (T/C) #1 instrumented at the upper part of the inner IFA closer to the center, T/C #2 and T/C #4 at the middle part of the inner IFA and T/C #18 and T/C #20 at the middle part of the outer IFA. Flow rates were measured, and the reactor thermal power and the average coolant temperature were determined from the measured flow

and temperature data. Reactivity feedback was inferred from the reflector position adjustments required to maintain core criticality at each power step. The feedback effects in these tests were expected to be dominated by the Doppler effects as the average coolant temperature was kept around 700 °F (644 K) to 760 °F.

Figure 1. (a) SEFOR Core I-E and Core I-J layout (b) Engineering drawing of a standard SEFOR fuel assembly (c) Axial view of a standard SEFOR fuel rod [1].

3. MODELING SEFOR ISOTHERMAL TESTS

Two ARC codes were employed to develop the deterministic models for SEFOR Core I-E and Core I-J. First, MC²-3 was used to generate 33-g multigroup cross sections [5] using the ENDF/B-VII.0 library [6]. These cross sections were then read by DIF3D-VARIANT [7] to perform full-core calculations and determine the core criticality, neutron flux distributions and power profiles.

The multigroup cross-section generation with MC²-3 followed a two-step procedure and produced the coarse energy group cross sections in ISOTXS files that can be read by DIF3D directly. In the first step, a series of transport calculations were carried out to obtain energy self-shielded cross sections for various regions of the reactor core, using a fine energy grid with over 1000 energy groups. For fuel regions, the 1-D cylindrical geometry model was used as illustrated in Figure 2 a). Other regions assumed to be infinite and were filled with a homogeneous mixture. The fine energy group cross sections for each region were used in modeling an approximate RZ model of the full SEFOR reactor core, taking into account the neutron leakage effects and spatial self-shielding effects in cross section generations. TWODANT [8] was the solver to calculate its fluxes. In the second step, MC²-3 imported these fluxes and used them to condense cross sections to the ANL 33-group structure.

For SEFOR, the available literature did not provide sufficient information to enable a fully detailed 3-D model outside its core region. The benchmark model for this project was developed by adopting the homogenized regions outside the reactor core based on a reference RZ model described in the original SEFOR report [1]. Figure 2 b) illustrates the DIF3D model for Core I-E, which deployed a regular HEX-

Z mesh and approximated the Downcomer regions (DC_IV, DC_OV), reflectors and shields using hexagons. Within the active core for each fuel channel, its detail geometry was explicitly considered in the MC²-3 for generating cross sections. The fuel assembly was radially homogenized in the DIF3D full-core model, while its axial geometry was explicitly modeled.

To compute core criticality and power distributions, volumetric flux distribution was assigned to each mesh or domain. A sixth-order polynomial was used for spatial approximations of both the source and flux distributions, while a first-order polynomial was applied for modeling neutron leakage. To account for anisotropic scattering effects, DIF3D-VARIANT solved the P3 neutron transport equation using vacuum boundary conditions.

Figure 2. (a) MC²-3 1-D cylindrical model for standard fuel assembly (b) DIF3D model for SEFOR Core I-E.

In the SEFOR isothermal tests, the measured reactivity feedback includes contributions from both Doppler broadening and core thermal expansions. These reactivity feedback effects in fast reactor safety analysis were modeled with reactivity feedback coefficients. For instance, the fuel Doppler coefficient accounts for the reactivity change due to changes in nuclear cross sections at different temperatures, the radial core expansion coefficient accounts for the radial core expansion, the fuel density coefficient accounts for fuel pin axial expansion, the sodium density coefficient accounts for the change in sodium density etc. These coefficients are typically assumed independent and the integral value of the different feedback coefficients within the core provide the estimation of the total reactivity feedback of the system.

In this benchmark study, the ARC deterministic model was used to calculate four different reactivity feedback effects separately: Doppler, fuel density, radial core expansion and coolant density. Nine temperature states with core temperatures varied from 350 °F to 750 °F (increments of 50 °F) were selected. Microscopic cross section sets were generated at each of these temperatures states to account for the Doppler effects. Reactivity feedback from radial core expansion was calculated by expanding the hexagon fuel lattice pitch. Feedback from axial core expansion was modeled by reducing the fuel density in each axial segment based on the thermal expansion coefficient of the MOX fuel. Feedback due to sodium density change was considered by reducing the sodium coolant density when temperature increased.

Figure 3 illustrates the calculated reactivity feedback from the four effects and compares the sum of these reactivity feedback with the SEFOR isothermal experimental data. A Serpent Monte Carlo model [9], which employs the same hexagon core layout but with the detail geometry simulated for each assembly, has also been developed for providing reference solutions [10]. The reactivity feedback was

calculated by adjusting the temperature libraries in each material and at the same time manually expanding the core geometries in all directions.

Figure 3. Comparison of the calculated reactivity feedback with experimental data from isothermal tests in SEFOR Core I-E.

As shown in Figure 3, both Serpent model and ARC model showed very good agreements with the experimental measurements. Furthermore, the ARC calculations breakdown of feedback contributions indicates that in SEFOR, Doppler feedback is the dominant mechanism, followed by radial core expansion. Sodium density changes and fuel axial expansions in both Core I-E only provide small reactivity feedback and the values are very close in this SEFOR core. All four feedback components were found to be negative. As excellent agreement was observed, this benchmark exercise demonstrates the accuracy of ANL ARC codes in predicting reactor feedback effects for SFRs using oxide fuel with temperatures up to about 670K.

4. MODELING SEFOR POWER ASCENDING TESTS

To simulate the power ascending tests, a similar reactor physics model using the ARC codes was also created for Core I-J to compute flux distributions and fission power distributions. PERSENT (PERturbation and SENSitivity for Transport) [11], which is developed based on the perturbation theory, was used to calculate the four types of reactivity feedback coefficients for Core I-J. A SAS model was developed to simulate heat transfer and changing temperatures as reactor power increased from 0.4 MW to 17.2 MW. For each power ascending test case, the ARC model computed the fission power distribution, which was then passed offline to the SAS model to determine the fuel temperature distribution. With fuel temperatures obtained from SAS model and reactivity feedback coefficients from PERSENT, the total reactivity feedback was then determined by integrating the coefficients over the active core temperature field.

The SAS model employed the single-pin channel model to calculate the temperature distributions of the fuel, cladding and coolant at steady state. A single fuel channel also included a structure component representing components like the wire wrap and assembly duct wall. Boundary conditions— such as flow rates, inlet coolant temperature, and system pressure—were specified based on measured values without simulating the complete primary coolant loop. As orifices were attached to the bottom grid plate of the SEFOR core, the fuel assemblies (except the center assembly for FRED) were grouped into six representative channels (channel 1 to channel 6) based on the orifice zone map, with relative flow rates matching specifications. This division of the reactor core is to capture the different flow conditions across the core. In addition, as shown in Figure 1 a), thermocouples were loaded in the two IFAs to measure fuel centerline temperatures during the power ascending tests. Therefore, two additional channels (channel 7 and channel 8) were created to model the local conditions where the IFAs were placed. Channel #7 represents the inner IFA closer to the core center and channel #8 represents the IFA

in core periphery. The flow rate on channel #7 was the same flow rate as channel #1 (same orifice zone) and the flow rate through channel #8 was the same as channel #6.

The SAS fuel channel model was radially and axially discretized into nodes for numerical simulations. The model covered regions from the homogenized grid plate (Na_GP_b) beneath the fuel rod to the upper homogenized zone (Na_steel) as shown in Figure 4, where seven zones were defined: three located below the active fuel, one zone representing the fuel region along with the upper Ni reflector, and three zones above the top axial reflector. In the radial direction, meshes in a reflector zone consist of two nodes, one in the coolant, and two in the structure to calculate the heat transfers. In the fuel region (zone 4), SAS uses a detailed treatment. The fuel region was modeled with nine nodes to resolve the temperature gradient across the pin, while the plenum was modeled as a single radial node.

Figure 4. Schematic of the axial zone divisions for SEFOR SAS single-pin channel model.

In the SAS model, the thermophysical properties of MOX fuel were taken from Carbajo’s review paper [12]. The thermophysical properties of SS316 were taken from BISON [13]. For SS304 structure materials, the same properties of SS316 were used. Heat conduction across the fuel pin gap was represented by the gap conductance:

$$\text{gap conductance} = \frac{HBPAR}{\text{gap}} \quad (4)$$

where, HBPAR is a user-defined parameter, and a helium thermal conductivity of 0.20 W/m-K was assumed. The denominator is the gap thickness. During the SEFOR power ascending tests (power from 0.4 MW to 17 MW), the average coolant temperature remained nearly constant at approximately 760 °F. Consequently, the gap thickness variations across power levels were primarily governed by the fuel pin thermal expansion, which was then dependent on the unknown fuel temperatures. Thus, an iterative process was adopted to determine the appropriate fuel-clad gap width for each test, channel, and axial node assuming that the initial pin has the cold dimension.

Figure 5 shows that the calculated fuel centerline temperatures converged after four iterations. When compared with experimental measurements from thermocouples, the SAS model predicted the temperature rise in the IFA rods near the core center reasonably well as shown in Figure 5 a) for T/C #1 and in Figure 5 b) for T/C #2 and #4). Results for T/C #18 and T/C #20 were not listed in this paper as experimental data showed a sudden increase of measured temperatures at the same power level around 5 MW. But results can be found in Ref. [10]. Overall, the ARC reactor physics model homogenized the fuel assemblies when calculating the reactor power in the IFAs. A detailed modeling of each fuel assembly with higher fidelity may improve the agreement. Some experimental uncertainty may also explain some of the differences.

Figure 5. Comparison of the calculated fuel centerline temperatures with the measured values by a) thermocouple #1 b) thermocouple #2 and #4.

Similarly to the isothermal testing, these coefficients were calculated independently. The Doppler coefficients were calculated by perturbing the nuclear cross section temperature. Reactivity feedback coefficients associated with fuel density changes (fuel axial expansion) and coolant density changes

were calculated by assuming a 1% reduction of the material density within each corresponding homogenized region. With these coefficients and the SAS calculated fuel-average temperatures in each channel, the reactivity feedback from sodium density change, fuel axial expansion and fuel Doppler were then obtained as shown in Figure 6. Feedback from the sodium density effects and fuel axial expansions in these tests are very small.

The feedback coefficient from radial core expansion used the result from the previous isothermal tests with temperatures at 760 °F. Figure 6 also compares the calculated total reactivity feedback with measurements assuming ~5% uncertainty in the experiments [2]. The ARC/SAS predictions were consistent with the experimental data within 1 σ . This benchmark analysis demonstrates that the ARC/SAS model can reliably predict Doppler reactivity feedback in a SFR like SEFOR under power operating conditions.

Figure 6. Comparison of the calculated and measured reactivity feedback for SEFOR power ascending tests in Core I-J.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This paper shows the benchmark work supported under the US DOE-NE FRP program of using SEFOR experimental data to validate ANL ARC reactor physics codes and the SAS4A/SASSYS-1 system analysis code in calculating Doppler reactivity feedback. Both the isothermal tests conducted in the zero-power experiments with fuel temperatures up to about 677 K and the power ascending tests with fuel temperatures extended up to 2500 K were successfully modeled, using the ARC codes for reactor physical calculation and the SAS code for heat transfer simulation. Comparisons with experimental data showed very good agreement between numerical results and experimental data. This benchmark work demonstrated the accuracy of these codes in modeling reactivity feedback in oxide fuel SFRs.

Future work will continue to use these codes to simulate the SEFOR reactivity insertion transients for assessing the numerical codes' capabilities of modeling Doppler reactivity feedback in SFR transients. In addition, supported by the DOE Nuclear Energy Advanced Modeling and Simulation (NEAMS) program, the SEFOR experimental data was also used to validate high-fidelity numerical tools such as Griffin [14] and Multiphysics coupling between Griffin and BISON under the MOOSE framework [15].

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